

Antibiotic Susceptibility of Bacteria Isolated from Poultry Feeds Sold in Ado Ekiti, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Poultry feed has been reported to be of potential risk to the animals consuming it and as a matter of public health importance. The aim of this research was to determine the antibiotic susceptibility of organisms isolated from the feed samples sold in Ado Ekiti. Twelve feed samples of four different brands were analyzed. The results showed that the microbial load of the grower mash ranged from 2.8×10^3 to 1.9×10^6 CFU/g, layers mash ranged between 3.0×10^4 and 8.3×10^6 CFU/g while the broiler starter was found to be between 5.6×10^4 and 3.6×10^7 CFU/g. Feed sample brand SBM have all time highest microbial load of 1.9×10^6 , 8.3×10^6 and 3.6×10^7 CFU/g for growers mash, layers mash and broiler starter respectively. The organisms isolated from the feed samples are *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* sp, *Salmonella* sp, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Bacillus* sp and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The antibiotic susceptibility showed that *Escherichia coli* isolated from the poultry feeds have highest resistance to Amoxicillin/Clavulinate (AUG) with 91.7%, while *Klebsiella* sp, *Salmonella* *Pseudomonas* sp *Bacillus* sp and *Staphylococcus aureus* showed highest resistance to Cloxicillin (CXC) with 91.7%, 87.5%, 100%, 88.9% and 80% respectively. Gentamicin (GEN) had the best antimicrobial activity in this research with only 7.1 % of the organisms being resistant.

Keyword: *Antibiogram, Escherichia coli, Grower mash, Poultry Feeds, Resistance, Salmonella.*

INTRODUCTION:

In the tropics, intensive animal husbandry utilizes a minimum of land and labour resources while providing an economically profitable resource of high quality protein for human consumption. In an effort to achieve rapid animal growth to meet the increasing demand for animal meat, large quantities of nitrogenous waste fortified with other supplements such as spent grain, cassava waste, bone meal etc. are compounded as animal feed [20]. Animal feed is an important component in animal production all over the world. Their composition includes mixtures of different raw materials from both plant and animal origins [4]. Feeds and feed ingredients comprise a large variety of products like cereals, soybeans, sunflower supplemented by fat, vitamins, minerals, antioxidants and meat meals [3, 15]. Feed had been reported to be a major vector for transmission of pathogens to farms and processing plants [22]. The quality of animal feed is of public health importance because it affects the quality of animal and the wholesomeness of meat consumed by man. Both pre-harvest and post-harvest biological contaminants can be transmitted via feed ingredients to the mixed feed and finally to animals.

Contaminated feed reduces the feed quality and can contribute to food-borne human illnesses through the feed-animal-food-human-chain. Contamination in animal feed is often originating from ingredients of both plant and animal sources, storage and unhygienic manufacturing processes [1, 13]. The quality and quantity of biological contaminants are largely affected by temperature and humidity. Reports of Gill and Best (1998) and Ruff (1992) [8, 23] had listed animal feed as one of the sources of microorganisms in animals, some of the additives have

been incriminated amongst the principal sources of bacteria of public health concern [18]. Various types of farm animal diseases and syndromes such as diarrhoea, bacillary dysentery, Salmonellosis, staphylococcosis, colibacillosis, erysipelas, listeriosis, have been traced to the contamination of animal feed [10]. A potential and more deadly hazard has been associated with the consumption of microbial toxins of bacterial and fungal origin in feed [11, 2, 7]. Considering the health hazard posed to animal and the unsuspecting consumers of such contaminated feeds and its overwhelming socioeconomic impact, it is pertinent to undertake this study. This research is therefore designed to identify, characterize and determine the antibiotic susceptibility of the bacterial flora present in animal feeds sold in Ado metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Sample Collection

Duplicate sample of four different brands of poultry feeds namely SBM, LMS, BMS, and MTO feeds were aseptically collected from 4 major markets in Ado-Ekiti. All samples were aseptically transported to the laboratory where bacteriological analysis were carried out within 2 hours of sample collection.

Determination of bacterial load

Five gram of each of the feed samples was aseptically weighed and homogenized in 45 ml of sterile buffer peptone water. Thereafter, ten-fold serial dilutions were done using the same diluents. One ml of appropriate dilution was aseptically plated, using pour plate technique, onto sterile plates of nutrient Agar (Biomark), MacConkey (Biomark) and *Salmonella-shigella* Agar

(Biomark) and incubated at 37°C for 24 h in an incubator (Royalcare England. DNP 9022A).

Enumeration of microbial population

After incubation at room temperature for 24h, colonies on nutrient agar plates were counted using the colony counter and the mean was recorded as total viable count (TVC). Enumeration of *Salmonella* was performed on *Salmonella-Shigella* agar plates. Total coliforms were determined on MacConkey agar plates.

Biochemical identification

The colonies were purified on nutrient agar plates followed by biochemical identification of colonies according to [14] Macfaddin (1980).

Antibiotic susceptibility

The antibiotic susceptibility was carried out by disc diffusion method on all the organisms isolated. The organisms were standardized using McFarland standard at the absorbance of 450nm. The samples were inoculated on Muller-Hinton agar. The following antimicrobial agents were tested: Cefazidime (CAZ 30 µg), Cefuroxime (CRX 30 µg), Gentamicin (GEN 10 µg), Ceftriaxone (CTR 30 µg), Erythromycin (ERY 5 µg), Cloxacillin (CXC 5 µg), Ofloxacin (OFL 5 µg), and Amoxicillin/Clavulinate (AUG 30 µg). Following the application of antimicrobial discs, the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h in an incubator

(Royalcare England. DNP 9022A). The diameters of the zones of inhibition were measured (millimetres) and were compared to internationally accepted measurements to determine the susceptibility or resistance of the isolate [21].

RESULT

The microbial load of the poultry feeds were showed in table 1, the microbial load of twelve feed samples from four different brands showed that the growers mash microbial load ranged from 2.8×10^3 to 1.9×10^6 CFU/g, the layers mash was between 3.0×10^4 and 8.3×10^6 CFU/g, while the broiler starter ranged between 5.6×10^4 and 3.6×10^7 CFU/g. Feed sample SBM had all time highest value with 1.9×10^6 , 8.3×10^6 and 3.6×10^7 CFU/g for growers mash, layers mash and broiler starter respectively. The feed samples analyzed also showed the presence of coliform in all the feeds, the coliform level ranged between 1.0×10^2 and 6.2×10^3 CFU/g for growers mash. The coliform level in layers mash ranged between 3.3×10^2 and 6.2×10^4 CFU/g while the in broiler starter ranged between 3.1×10^2 and 2.1×10^4 CFU/g. It is note wordy to find out that only one feed sample had no *Salmonella* contamination (LMS grower mash), other feed samples had *Salmonella* ranging from 2.0×10^1 and 6.0×10^3 CFU/g.

Table 1: The Microbial load, coliform count and salmonella

Source of feed		Microbial load (CFU/g)	Coliform load (CFU/g)	Salmonella (CFU/g)
Grower Mash	SBM	1.9×10^6	2.0×10^3	1.0×10^2
	LMS	2.8×10^3	1.0×10^2	-
	BMS	4.3×10^3	3.0×10^2	2.0×10^1
	MTO	6.1×10^4	6.2×10^3	3.2×10^2
Layers Mash	SBM	8.3×10^6	6.2×10^4	3.0×10^2
	LMS	4.0×10^6	7.3×10^2	7.2×10^1
	BMS	3.0×10^4	3.3×10^3	6.0×10^3
	MTO	6.3×10^4	3.3×10^2	6.1×10^1
Broiler Starter	SBM	3.6×10^7	2.1×10^4	1.6×10^2
	LMS	5.6×10^4	3.2×10^3	2.1×10^2
	BMS	9.1×10^6	2.0×10^3	4.2×10^1
	MTO	1.2×10^5	3.1×10^2	3.2×10^1

The organisms isolated were subjected to biochemical test as showed in table 2, organisms isolated include *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* sp, *Salmonella* sp, *Pseudomonas* sp, *Bacillus* sp, and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Table 2: Biochemical reaction of the isolates.

Cultural characteristics	Gram reaction	Motility	Catalase	Oxidase	Coagulase	Indole	Methyl-red	Voges-Proskauer	Citrate	H ₂ S production	Nitrate	Urease	Probable Organism
Large cream with rhizoid – like edge on nutrient agar	+ rod	+	+	-	ND	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	<i>Bacillus</i> spp
flat, greenish colonies	- rod	+	+	+	ND	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp
round convex colonies	- rod	+	+	-	ND	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
smooth round convex pale Colonies	- rod	+	+	-	ND	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Salmonella</i> spp
Yellow and smooth colony	+ cocci	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Mucoid, pink colony on MacConkey agar.	- rod	-	+	-	ND	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp

Table 3: Antibiotic resistance pattern of isolate in percentages (%)

Isolates	CAZ	CRX	GEN	CTR	ERY	CXC	OFL	AUG
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (n=24)	16.7	50.0	12.5	79.2	62.5	87.5	41.7	91.7
<i>Klebsiella</i> sp (n=12)	50.0	33.3	0	58.3	33.3	91.7	8.3	25.0
<i>Salmonella</i> sp (n=16)	43.8	56.3	18.8	62.5	62.5	87.5	18.8	87.5
<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp (n=8)	37.5	50.0	0	37.5	50.0	100	12.5	37.5
<i>Bacillus</i> sp (n=9)	55.6	33.3	11.1	22.2	11.1	88.9	22.2	44.4
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (n=10)	50	60	0	40	30	80	0	70
Total	42.3	47.2	7.1	50	41.6	89.3	17.3	59.4

Ceftazidime (CAZ 30 µg), Cefuroxime (CRX 30 µg), Gentamicin (GEN 10 µg), Ceftriaxone (CTR 30 µg), Erythromycin (ERY 5 µg), Cloxicillin (CXC 5 µg), Ofloxacin (OFL 5 µg), Amoxicillin/Clavulinate (AUG 30 µg).

DISCUSSION

Animal feeds have been listed as one of the sources of microbes of farmed animals and poultry [24]. This study revealed that six bacterial were isolated in the feed sample analyzed, thus the bacterial recovered may indicate a potential hazard to the animals. The occurrence of bacterial species of public health concern may indicate obvious health hazard in terms of direct consumption of bacteriological contaminated feed or their toxins by farmed animal [6, 19].

Animal feeds are rich source of nutrient for microbial growth especially when the environmental conditions are favourable. Monitoring of microbial contamination of animal production environment is an important first step in determining how such contaminants pass through the food chain [12]. In this research it was found that the microbial load of feed sample SBM was higher than what is recorded for every other feed samples, this may likely have resulted from the manufacturer or the ingredients used in compounding the feed since good manufacturing practices often enhances good products [9].

In a similar research carried out by [24] Uwaezuoke and Ogbulie, (2008) the presence of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* was reported which is in line with what was observed in this research. The result of the microbial load of the feed samples in this research was lower than what was reported by [5] David and Ogunlade (2013) who reported the microbial load ranging between 7.58×10^5 and 6.36×10^6 CFU/g for feed samples produced by local industries.

The level of coliform contamination of bacteria in this study is an indication of poor hygiene and lack of good manufacturing environment. Although the coliform count level was found to be lower than what was reported by [5] David and Ogunlade (2013) who reported a range of 2.85×10^2 and 4.40×10^4 CFU/g. On the other hand, the presence of *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* species may suggest faecal as well as environmental contamination. Some of these organisms are well known pathogens of birds and farmed animals. [17, 24]. *E. coli* for example was reportedly implicated in disease conditions such as colibacillosis which occurs in forms such as enteric and septicaemic colibacillosis whereas *Salmonella* and *Staphylococcus aureus* are capable of producing acute and chronic infections in all or most types of birds and animals [17].

The presence of salmonella in the feed is also of public health importance, this is because, in general the transmission of *Salmonella* sp through the environment has been shown to be cyclic, and poultry feeds had been reportedly viewed as important links for contamination in poultry [15, 25] Although little is

known about the relative significance of different sources of contamination of poultry feeds, it may depend partially upon the contamination levels of individual feed ingredients used in mixing the feed [9, 16].

The antibiotic susceptibility test carried out on the organisms showed that some of the organisms have the ability to resist some of the common antibiotic. It was also observed that most of the microorganisms showed resistance to cloxicillin. The high sensitivity of the isolated organisms to GEN, ERY and CTR could be related to less frequent usage of these drugs for therapeutic purposes, therefore reducing the chance for resistance to develop [26].

In the light of the potential risk associated with the type of organisms present in poultry feeds sold around Ado Ekiti metropolis, the microbial contaminations of the feeds should be reduced to the barest minimal. Since the climatic condition of the study area favours the growth of bacteria, production and storage must be appropriate, bearing in mind the risks contaminations pose on the safety of the animals and public health. Chemical amendment, heat treatment, irradiation and careful sourcing of materials are proven methods of reducing bacterial loads in feed ingredient.

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